

School-Based Management Evaluators: Strengthening Stakeholders' Protocol

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Abstract. The study was conducted to describe the school-based management evaluation framework, thus preventing its method from reviewing mechanisms in Pantukan South District, Davao Oriental, post-pandemic. A qualitative research design was used, and assumptions regarding selecting participants and ethics in collecting, analyzing, and interpreting data were considered. Respondents were SBM Evaluator members among schools in the Division of Mati City, using facilitating questions to draw out narratives on their experiences, challenges, and coping mechanisms and further learning insights given their undertakings as multi-grade teachers in post-pandemic. Experiences among SBM evaluators include being challenged with perspectives, threatened with validity and reliability, and having differed interpretations. Coping mechanisms were shared through building harmonious working relationships and collaboration and cooperation. Despite experiences, challenges, and learning insights shared, through reviewing policy framework, advocate CI mechanism and upskills proficiency competence. SBM evaluation will depend on the evolving needs and priorities of education governance. Integration of technology, emphasis on equity, focus on student outcomes, collaboration and knowledge-sharing, and adaptation to changing needs are all possible future directions for SBM evaluations. Evaluation can continue to be a valuable tool for improving governance and promoting high-quality education.

KEY WORDS

1. School-based Management 2. Stakeholders' Protocol 3. Governance

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1. Introduction

The Millennium Development Goal highlights explicitly the need to increase literacy rates among youth. However, it is important to understand what types of programs that actually have positive and persistent effects on literacy levels and academic performance. Initiatives which call for universal primary education, have pushed developing countries to extend primary school access (Kumler, 2019). Yet increases in the quantity of schools have not always led to corresponding increases in the quality of the education offered, and in many developing countries, the reading ability of many students is well below the appropriate level for their grade. Reports stated that though the Philippine government spends 16 percent of its budget on education, most of its expenditures are focused on staff salaries, with very little money left over for training, textbooks or buildings (Ning, Van Damme, Van Den Noortgate, Yang, Gie-

len, 2015). School-based management in the United States has historically been good and provided support (Brokamp, Houtveen, van de Grift, *The Relationship among Students' Reading Performance, Their Classroom Behavior, and Teacher Skills*, 2019). Though the majority of school heads in the United States use core leadership skills programs to design and deliver effective management, virtually nothing is known about how stakeholders interact with core programs to develop effective management (Noyce, 2020). Amidst its growing number of people, the Philippine government has remained steadfast to convert dense population into productive and literate individuals, the pillar of a strong nation. The Department of Education highlighted that literacy empowers people to become responsive and worthy individuals not only in the school system and its policy and program implementation but as well as for their personal development that will later be translated into valuable contributions to the community, the nation, and the world (Elvira S. Balinas, 2017). This calls to action that an effective school-based management implementation must be seriously carried out throughout the school system. This must develop competence among school leaders, and it must be based on proven practices. Moreover, there are three components that are critical to the design, implementation, and sustainability of powerful management and operations; these are professional development that equips educators with a solid knowledge base, effective instructional tools that are aligned to the knowledge base, and school systems that support and nurture implementation. (Brokamp, Houtveen, van de Grift, *The Relationship among Students' Reading Performance, Their Classroom Behavior, and Teacher Skills*, 2019). Although not all school programs and projects are alike, many published programs claim to be based on research; few actually live up to that claim. Research supports the need for explicit strategies for improving school performance and advocacy for continuous improvement (Gonzalez, McCraney, Panesar-Aguilar, Cale, 2020). Meanwhile, the country has taken initiatives in response to the elusive dream of effective and improved school performance. Thus, the Department of Education (DepEd) directly addresses its thrust to make every school perform best in its context. The evaluation process, however, has been misappreciated by some, if not all, evaluators, for they assess schools based on their perspectives instead of the expected outcomes and not on the totality and reality of the authenticity of the performance. (Judith L. Irvin, 2020). In the local context, Schools in Davao de Oro Division are still experiencing issues with evaluation skills among authorities, which has caused much alarm. Teachers, learners, and other stakeholders are facing challenges, which creates anxiety among school system stakeholders since it would be difficult for them to be guided and enhance the mechanisms for advancing school improvement and performance. Schools must plan carefully, implement effectively, monitor efficiently, and evaluate the performance of learners, including soundly. In Pantukan South District, Schools are currently assessing their performance on school-based management implementation, including general scholastic average grades of the learners, nutritional levels, reading abilities, and the like. This is in preparation for the next three-year cycle School Improvement Plan and Annual Implementation Plan. Schools need to conduct assessments and identify priority improvement areas to develop sound planning and determine significant inputs to prepare for implementation. Thus, this study was conducted to generate sound information as inputs to quality planning in the next cycle, to come up with sound outcomes, and to become relevant to the approaches and styles of assessing school management and performance. In order for this to happen, this study intends to assess the school-based Management

Program implementation and evaluation scheme for the past three school years with respect to the School's planning, implementation, monitoring, and evaluation processes.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—The purpose of this phenomenological research study was to describe how the school-based management system is appreciated in terms of evaluating a school's performance given leadership and governance, curriculum and instruction, accountability and continuous improvement, and community partnerships. At this stage in the re-

- (1) What are the lived experiences of evaluators in evaluating school-based management in Pantukan South District Schools, Davao de Oro, during post-pandemic?
- (2) How do school-based management evaluators cope with challenges?
- (3) What educational management insights can be drawn from the school-based management evaluators in post-pandemic?

1.3. Significance of the Study—The proposed study is of significance to the following stakeholders, where the researcher has taken inspiration. The preview of this study it focuses on the beneficiaries of the following:

School Principals – School Heads are the captains of their respective ship, and they lead the teachers in the crafting and setting of the School Improvement Plan and Annual Implementation Plans as an indicator input of school-based management practices. One of the key result area performances of the school head is to make the school conducive for learning, where learners and other stakeholders hold on to the idea that school is a second home of the young generation of the locality and needs to be safe, friendly, and haven-like. The study results will be significant to the school head where its sustainability in the operation of school-based management is significant for academic performance and future generation of learners. Teachers – Teachers are the model builders and makes a strong influence among learners. Teachers are facilitators of learning, and at the same time, they are the ones who make the school-based

search, school heads and teachers are empowered to implement school-based management and development despite its cessation to reevaluate the process of appreciation in terms of its evaluation mechanism.

1.2. Research Questions—This study described the school-based management evaluation framework, thus cessation of its method to review mechanism in Pantukan South District, Davao Oriental, in post-pandemic. It sought to answer to the following inquiries:

management system possible. The study's result will help enhance curriculum implementation, and thus, learners are expected to exhibit high academic performance. This also could contribute to the inputs of another planning cycle given post pandemics where school are starting to gear up into newer learning facilitation process. The results will provide teachers inputs on adjusting the significance of their respective roles in the school as a learning community where learners feel safe and increase academic performance. Learners – Learners are beneficiaries of the all programs and projects are the direct consumers of all efforts of the teachers in the facilitation of school-based management. The study's results shall provide learners with more opportunities to learn and improve academic performance; the school heads' leadership, sacrificial efforts of the teachers, and the details of their management and implementation of their curriculum and governance activities will provide opportunities for academic and learning improvements. Parents – In the current pedagogical approaches, parents play a significant role in developing children's learn-

ing styles. They serve as scaffolds for learners' learning modalities. The study's results would help parents enhance their awareness and skills in assisting learners in developing an attitude of empowering techniques at school and home. Local Barangay Units – Local officials in the barangay play political leadership where their influence can change the perspectives among community members. They will serve as the vehicle to sustain the school programs, projects, and activities throughout the school-based management system. The study results could be an input to their local barangay program in redirecting strategies to upskill education committees to revisit plans, programs, and projects in collaboration with significant others in upholding effective school-based management practices. This would start in the family as children learn the skills from school, thus expanding to community practice and eventually making their everyday lifestyle. Future Researchers – The study results could be a good starting point for further research and replication studies in other schools and communities in Davao de Oro and throughout the country.

Therewith, to guarantee the understanding of the terms applied in the said study, the following are defined conceptually and operationally: School-based Management. The term refers to school-based management as one of the guiding policies of the Department of Education, where the school has been given the liberty to operate and manage according to its own context, given the culture of the locality. In this study, latent variables are used as the theme, and latent variables are based on the practices provided by each indicator for every given principle of SBM, namely, leadership and governance, curriculum and instruction, accountability and continuous improvement, and resource management. This furthers the program, evaluated per school year and on a medium-term plan and implementation to track school performance given indicators. . Cessation to Strengthen Mechanism Evaluation.

This refers to the mode set, approaches, techniques, and styles of monitoring and evaluating School-Based Management performance during post-pandemic, given stakeholders' experiences during non-face-to-face operation. Thus, newer approaches must be developed and discovered as newer intervention approaches. In this study, latent variables include document analysis, discussion between and among stakeholders, and direct observations. However, the evaluation process has to be reviewed, for, in this context, the evaluation and its content have to be reappreciated based solely on the context and how SBM is operationalized during non-face-to-face school management and operation.

1.4. Review of Significant Literature— This section presents literature on the experiences, challenges, and insights of School-Based Management (SBM) evaluators, particularly during the post-pandemic period. It explores the principles, challenges, coping mechanisms, and educational insights drawn from SBM evaluation.

*1.4.1. Lived Experiences of SBM Evaluators—*SBM empowers educators, parents, and community members in decision-making to enhance student outcomes. Robbins and Alvy (2015) emphasize a strong commitment to SBM goals, engagement with stakeholders, awareness of internal and external factors (Murphy et al., 2016), and continuous improvement (Creighton Rorrer, 2020). These principles enable evaluators to enhance school effectiveness.

*1.4.2. Challenged Perspectives—*Differing stakeholder perspectives complicate SBM evaluation. Creswell (2015) highlights the role of cultural competence in managing these differences, while Wilmot and Hocker (2018) stress dialogue and collaboration. In the Philippines, the shift to K-12 and technological integration (Esquivel, 2018) further diversifies perspectives. Strategies like participatory evaluation (Bautista, 2019) and reflection (Meris, 2016) promote inclusivity.

1.4.3. Threatened Validity and Reliability—SBM evaluation faces risks of inaccuracy due to unclear criteria and resistance from stakeholders (Singh Garg, 2018; Dika Rachmawati, 2017). Triangulation and stakeholder involvement enhance reliability (Brown Gustafson, 2018; Kenworthy Gertig, 2015). In the Philippines, evaluators often lack training (Tuy, 2015) and face pressure for favorable results (Cahapay, 2017). Transparency, stakeholder engagement, and training (Cajilig, 2017) address these challenges.

1.4.4. Differed Interpretation—Stakeholders interpret SBM results based on varied priorities (Wei Li, 2019). Conflicting interests (Cheng, 2015) and cultural influences (Munir, 2017) further complicate interpretations. Effective communication, stakeholder training, and participatory approaches improve clarity (Fernandez, 2020).

1.4.5. Coping Strategies in SBM Evaluation—SBM evaluators adapt by embracing new methods, engaging stakeholders, and fostering collaboration (Zainuddin Perera, 2019). Fun-based learning enhances engagement (Nasititi Ulfah, 2021), while collaboration mitigates challenges (Ali Waseem, 2021; Tiamzon et al., 2019). Building harmonious relationships (Gonzales, 2022) and cooperative evaluation approaches (Fajardo et al., 2019) support effective implementation.

1.4.6. Educational Management Insights—SBM evaluation highlights the importance of leadership, community engagement, and resource management (Rosales Reyes, 2019). Reviewing policies enhances implementation clarity (Tariman et al., 2021), while advocating continuous improvement fosters adaptability (Jimenez et al., 2019; Santos, 2021). Upskilling through professional development and technology integration ensures evaluators remain effective (Reyes De Guzman, 2020; Garcia De Vera, 2019).

SBM evaluation provides insights into gov-

ernance, stakeholder engagement, and school improvement. Addressing challenges through training, collaboration, and policy review enhances its effectiveness, ensuring continuous educational progress.

1.5. Synthesis—In-school based management evaluation is crucial because it provides a structured way for schools to assess their own performance, identify areas for improvement, and make data-driven decisions to enhance student learning outcomes by empowering local stakeholders to participate in the decision-making process actively and hold themselves accountable for the results, ultimately leading to a more responsive and effective school environment. The importance of the evaluators in school management can be of great significance in improving the program that would lead to academic success. Likewise, stakeholder involvement in education plays an important part, as the purpose of each stakeholder is to reach a common educational goal through team effort. When multiple stakeholders are engaged, the team effort increases the chances of success in reaching these goals. Evaluators and stakeholders bring insight and skills that help to create the learning community. Stakeholders are people, and education is a people business. As schools develop productive relationships with all stakeholders, they gain feedback and are able to reflect. Effective communication is essential for quality school operation.

1.6. Theory—This study is anchored on the theory of program evaluation by Alkin (1972), who proposed that the purpose of evaluation theory is to predict fully the appropriateness of utilizing various evaluation strategies within a system. Theory-based evaluation is an approach to evaluation, whether a conceptual or analytical model and not a specific method or technique. It is a way of structuring and undertaking analysis in an evaluation. A theory of change explains how an intervention is expected to produce its results. Some pretty popu-

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

lar evaluation methods are input measurement, output or performance measurement, impact or outcomes assessment, quality assessment, process evaluation, benchmarking, standards, cost analysis, organizational effectiveness, program evaluation methods, and LIS-centered methods. Evaluation theory does more than help us make sound judgments about what kind of methods to use, under what circumstances, and toward what forms of evaluation influence. Second, comparing evaluation theories is a helpful way of identifying and better understanding the key areas of debate within the field. All four major elements of a good theory - philosophical, descriptive, prescriptive, and evaluative - must be present for the theory's positive benefit in counseling. Ultimately, the test of a good theory will be how well it supports your interactions with specific clients. Moreover, evaluation is the systematic assessment of an initiative's design, implementation, or results for learning or decision-making. Systematic: An evaluation should be as systematic and impartial as possible (UNEG, 2005). Evaluation provides a systematic method to study a program, practice, intervention, or initiative to understand how well it achieves its goals. Evaluations help determine what works well and what could be improved in a program or initiative. Evaluation is a systematic process that aims to understand what a program does and how well it does. Evaluation results can be used to maintain or improve pro-

gram quality and to ensure that future planning can be more evidence-based. Such benefits to the organization include enhancing the chance that the initiative's goals and objectives are being achieved, determining value for money (i.e., allocated resources are yielding the most significant benefit for clients and stakeholders, and identifying what components of an initiative work/do not work and why. This study's evaluation of school-based management schools provides opportunities for school heads and other stakeholders to track and improve performance, provided that the working environment and conditions are constant. Due to the pandemic, the school-based management system has shifted in a different direction, making the school head fit the circumstance where all indicators of the school-based management system must be considered and considered. Thus, in this study, the SBM evaluation provides an opportunity to review the process and steps to make a sound decision for the school heads and other stakeholders to consider shifts in the operation and management of curriculum and school governance. Given this, the school-based evaluation team has to review all mechanisms of the processes to ensure that the validity and reliability of results align with the standards given the context of the current circumstance. This is where they vary since some schools have the context of non-face-to-face modalities while others are blended in their governance and operations.

2. Methodology

This chapter of the study presents the qualitative design method, research participants, data collection, role of the researcher, data analysis, trustworthiness of the study, and ethical considerations. This details the operational implementation of the methodology used in the study. The main sources of the concepts were taken from the respective authors who established the foundation for qualitative research methods. Each section is thoroughly conceptualized to establish authority and ethical standards in the process of collection, analysis, and interpretation. The three most common qualitative methods are participant observation, in-depth interviews, and focus groups. Each method was particularly suited for obtaining a specific type of data. Participant observation was appropriate for collecting data on naturally occurring behaviors in their usual contexts. In-depth Interviews (IDI) were optimal for collecting data on individuals' personal histories, perspectives, and experiences, mainly when exploring sensitive topics. Focus groups effectively elicit data on a group's cultural norms and generate broad overviews of issues of concern to the cultural groups or subgroups represented. Patton (2002) defined phenomenology as an inquiry that asks the question, "What is the structure and essence of the experience of his phenomenon for these people?" "the goal of this research worked well with this definition in trying to understand the experiences of the BE Coordinators as they try to compare its implementation then and now. Giorgi (2007) cautioned researchers to be prepared for an investigation greater in depth and breadth than the offered description implied. He suggested that information be viewed as only the tip of the iceberg.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—The philosophical assumption is a framework used to collect, analyze, and interpret data in a specific field. It establishes the background used to reach conclusions and decisions. Typical philosophical assumptions have different types and are elaborated below. Good research begins with selecting the topic, problem, or area of interest, as well as the paradigm. Stanage (1987) traces 'paradigm' back to its Greek (paradigm) and Latin origins (paradigm), meaning pattern, model, or example among examples, an exemplar or model to follow according to which design actions are taken. Differently stated, a paradigm was an action of submitting to a view. This view was supported by Denzin and Lincoln (2000), who defend a research paradigm as a "basic set of beliefs that guide action," dealing with first principles, "ultimates" or the researcher's worldview or philosophy. Ontology. This part of the research pertains to how the issue relates to the nature of reality. According to Creswell (2012), reality is subjective and multiple, as seen by the study participants. The ontological issue addresses the nature of reality for the qualitative researcher. The reality was constructed by individuals involved in the research situation. Thus, multiple realities exist, such as the realities of the researcher, those of individuals being investigated, and those of the reader or audiences interpreting the study. In this study, the experiences of SBM Evaluators are discussed by the participants, and tries to look into their strategies in addressing the challenges and educational insights. In this study, the researcher relied on voices and interpretations of the participants through extensive quotes and themes that reflected their words and provided evidence of different perspectives. The participants' answers to the study were coded and analyzed to build and construct for the commonality and discreteness of responses. The responses of the participants were carefully coded to ensure the reliability of the result.

The researcher upheld the authenticity of the responses and precluded from making personal bias as the study progressed. Epistemology. This refers to the awareness of how knowledge claims are justified by staying as close to the participants as possible during the study to obtain firsthand information. Guba and Lincoln, as cited by Creswell (2012), state that on the epistemological assumption, the researcher attempted to lessen the distance between himself or herself from the participants. He suggests that, as a researcher, he or she collaborates, spends time in the field with participants, and becomes an 'insider'. Based on Davidson (2000) and Jones (2011). The researcher identified phenomenology with the use of thematic analysis as the best means for this type of study. In this regard, individual researchers "hold explicit belief." This study intended to gather information from the participants or teachers in Pantukan South, Davao De Oro, as to how the implement SBM evaluation during the pandemic. It is assumed that close interaction with the participants was established to gain direct information that would shed light on the knowledge behind the inquiry, particularly on the experiences and strategies used in school-based management evaluations to strengthen the mechanism. Axiology. It refers to the role of values in research. Creswell (2012) avers that the role of values in a study was significant. Axiology suggests that the researcher openly discusses values that shape the narrative and includes their interpretation in conjunction with the interpretation of participants. Upholding the dignity and value of every detail of information obtained from the participants was ensured by the researcher. The researcher understands the personal and value-laden nature of information gathered from the study. Therefore, the researcher preserved the merit of the participants' answers and carefully interpret the answers in the light of the participants' interpretation. Rhetoric. It means that reporting what reality was through the eyes of

the research participants. This was important because it means that the research would report objectively on what was observed and heard from the participants. The research used personal voice and qualitative terms and limited definition. In the context of the study, the researcher used the first person to the elucidation the experiences of teachers as they went on school-based management evaluation during post-pandemic.

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—The methodology was different from the method. The methodology is a creative and responsive approach to understanding questions and subject matter, while the method refers to the exact knowledge and procedure (Gerodias, 2013). In this study, the challenges experienced by the SBM Evaluators to cease to strengthen mechanisms in Pantukan South District were gathered through an In-Depth Interview (IDI) as well as their coping mechanisms were extracted from the participants. The researcher's drive in knowing the deeper meaning of the challenges experienced by SBM evaluators became the basis for doing qualitative research, a means which Kalof and Dietz (2008), as cited from Gerodias (2013) considered helpful in looking for "meanings and motivations that underline cultural symbols, personal experiences, and phenomena." By using phenomenology, this need was hoped to be addressed by bringing the challenges experienced by SBM evaluators during post-pandemic in a manner that, as David (2005) wrote, the themes, symbols, and meaning of the experiences presented. Phenomenological research was based on two premises. The first was that experience was a valid, rich, and rewarding source of knowledge. According to Becker (1992), as cited in Morrissey Higgs (2006), that experience is a source of knowledge and shapes one's behavior. From the definition, human experience was viewed as a cornerstone of knowledge about human phenomena and not an unreliable source. The second premise of

phenomenological research lies in the view that the everyday world is a valuable and productive source of knowledge and that we can learn much about ourselves and reap key insights into the nature of an event by analyzing how it occurs in our daily lives (Morrissey Higgs, 2006). By doing phenomenology, which is concerned with the "what" and the "how" (Moustakas, 1995), the researcher projected that the challenges experienced, mechanisms used by the SBM evaluators were explored, and insights drawn as the basis for the possible future research and policy analysis about this research.

2.3. Design and Procedure—This study employed a qualitative approach to research, specifically a phenomenological research design. According to Creswell (2012), phenomenology was an approach to qualitative research focused on the commonality of lived experiences within a particular group. The fundamental goal of the approach was to arrive at a description of the nature of the particular phenomenon. Typically, interviews were conducted with individuals who have first-hand knowledge of an event, situation, or experience. Other forms of data, such as documents, observations, and art, were also used. The data were read and reread and were culled for phrases and themes that were grouped into clusters of meanings. Through this process, the researcher constructed the universal meaning of the event, situation, or experience and arrived at a more profound understanding of the phenomenon. Moreover, Maxwell (2013) also added that with its roots in philosophy, psychology, and education, phenomenology attempts to extract the purest, untainted data, and in some interpretations of the approach, bracketing was used by the researcher to document personal experiences with the subject to help remove him or herself from the process. One method of bracketing is taking notes. According to Corbetta (2003), the phenomenological research design was a qualitative type of research for which interviews

provide an in-depth method that can grant access to deep knowledge and explanations and help grasp the subjects' perspective. Creswell (2012) also claimed that interviews were primarily done in qualitative research and occur when researchers ask one or more participants general, open-ended questions and record their answers. Often, audio tapes were utilized to allow more consistent transcription. Interviews are also helpful for following up with individual respondents after questionnaires, such as to investigate their responses further. In qualitative research, interviews were used to pursue the meanings of central themes in the world of their subjects. The main task in doing interviews was to understand the meaning of what the interviewees said (McNamara, 1999). Withal, based on the statements of Quad (2016), the researcher transcribed and typed the data into a computer file in order to analyze it after interviewing. Interviews exceptionally be useful for uncovering the story behind a participant's experiences and pursuing in-depth information around a topic. The researcher collected data from individuals who have experienced the phenomenon under investigation, typically via long interviews. Next, the data analysis involved triangulation, extracting significant statements from the transcribed interviews. The significant statements were transformed into clusters of meanings according to how each statement fell under specific psychological and phenomenological concepts. Moreover, these transformations were tied together to make a general description of the experience, both the textural description of what was experienced and the structural description of how it was experienced. The researcher incorporated his or her meaning of the experiences here. Finally, the report was written so that readers could better understand the essential, invariant structure of the essence of the experience. Conversely, several challenges have been pointed out. The researcher required a solid grounding in the philosophical guidelines

of phenomenology. The subjects selected for the study were individuals who had actually experienced the phenomenon. The researcher needed to bracket his or her own experiences and observations, which was difficult to do. The researcher also needed to decide how and when his or her observations should be incorporated into the study. Epistemologically, phenomenological approaches were based on the paradigm of personal knowledge and subjectivity and emphasized the importance of personal perspective and interpretation. As such, they were powerful tools for understanding subjective experience, gaining insights into people's motivations and actions, and cutting through the cluster of taken-for-granted assumptions and conventional wisdom. Since this study focuses on exploring and assessing the SBM evaluators' experience and feelings toward the evaluation mechanisms, the researcher intends to employ phenomenological qualitative research methods.

2.4. Ethical Considerations—Ethical considerations are significant in the design of this research study. The researcher needed to consider several ethical issues regarding the research participant in this fieldwork. Ethical considerations can be specified as one of the most important parts of the research. The researcher needs to adhere to the aims of the research, imparting authentic knowledge, truth, and prevention of error.

2.4.1. Social Value—The research was essential to society. In this study, the social value was focused on the experience of teachers. SBM evaluators specifically conducted this study. This study also served as a basis for the higher authorities to create more programs and resolutions from which all teachers and school stakeholders could benefit. Thus, the social problem that pushes the researcher's interest is the challenges faced by the SBM evaluators to augment the process of evaluation mechanism. Informed Consent – In the conduct and practice of this study, the Treaty Principle of

Participation, as cited by McLeod (2009), was adhered to. The invitation to the participants ensured that their participation in the research was completely voluntary and based on understanding adequate information. The recruitment and selection of participants are lodged in the appendices of this study. Gaining the trust and support of research participants was critical to informed and ethical academic inquiry and phenomenological research (Walker, 2007, as cited by Pillerin, 2012). All participants were given an informed consent form before scheduling the interviews and participating in the phenomenological research process. Each participant was required to provide a signed personal acknowledgment, consent, and an indication of a willingness to participate in the study release. The informed consent letter aims to introduce the research effort, provide contact information, articulate the study's intent, request voluntary participation by the recipients, and anticipate the information the informants were expected to provide. All participants were required to sign and return the consent letter to the researcher before participating.

2.4.2. Vulnerability of Research Participants—This study's participants could answer the research instrument, for they are all professional teachers in public elementary schools. Thus, the researcher assured them that as the researcher, he or she can easily be reached through the contact number and address in case there are some clarifications or questions about the study.

2.4.3. Risks, Benefits, and Safety—The recruitment of the respondents was free of coercion, undue influence, or inducement. Moreover, respondents were provided with the contact numbers of the panel chair or panel members in case they had queries related to the study. Furthermore, if respondents experienced potential discomfort and inconvenience while answering the questions, they were not compelling to participate in any manner. Further, the researcher ensured the respondents were safe dur-

ing the survey and interview. Thus, the questionnaire was distributed in a safe venue and administered at their convenience. The dominant concern of this study was the Treaty Principle of Protection, as reflected in the respect for the rights of privacy and confidentiality and the minimization of risk. This was done by assigning pseudonyms for each informant so as not to disclose their identity. The possibility of a degree of risk inherent to this was minimized by taking all reasonable steps to guarantee participant confidentiality.

2.4.4. Privacy and Confidentiality of Information—This study observed the Data Privacy Act of 2002 to ensure that the data cannot be traced back to their actual sources to protect participants' identities. Thus, utmost care was taken to ensure the anonymity of the data sources. Hence, any printed output that was carried out from this study was kept in anonymity. Furthermore, all the issues were considered so there would be no conflict of interest between the researcher and the respondents. Any misleading information and representation of primary data findings in a biased way must be avoided.

2.4.5. Justice—The respondents were informed of the researcher's role and their corresponding role during data gathering. They were briefed that they had to answer the survey questions honestly and that any communication related to the research should be done honestly. Similarly, they were informed that they would benefit first from the study's results.

2.4.6. Transparency—The study's results were accessed by the respondent's heads of the participating schools because the information is available and will be placed on CDs or other storage devices, which the researcher can request to provide. In addition, by learning about the study's results, classroom teachers will be aware of the significance of the study and its contribution to their well-being. Further, each participant was advised that they have the right

to withdraw their information at any time up to the completion of the data collection process. They can be requested and allowed to verify their transcript after the interview. This allowed the participants to amend or remove any information they felt might identify them. The researcher reserved the right to use pseudonyms and change names and/or non-significant dates in the interest of protecting the participant's identity in all subsequent data analysis and reporting.

2.4.7. Qualification of the Researcher—The researcher ensured that he or she was qualified to conduct the study. The researcher should complete the academic requirements and pass the comprehensive examination before writing the thesis, the last requirement to obtain the master's degree. The researcher should also be qualified to conduct the study physically, mentally, emotionally, and financially. In addition, the advisee-adviser tandem ensured that the study would reach its completion.

2.4.8. Adequacy of Facilities—The researcher strived to complete the study successfully in the specified time and was equipped with the necessary resources. Likewise, the technical committee helped enhance the paper by giving suggestions and recommendations. The researcher also ensured that he or she had enough funds to continue and finish the research. Thus, this study was hoped to be completed within the target time.

2.4.9. Community Involvement—The researcher respected the respondents' local traditions, culture, and views in this study. Moreover, this study did not involve any use of deceit in any stage of its implementation, specifically in the recruitment of the participants or methods of data collection. Furthermore, the researcher necessarily expressed great pleasure in the interviewees' wholehearted participation in the study. Plagiarism And Fabrication As The Researcher – The researcher respected other works by properly citing the author and rewriting what

someone else has said in his or her way. The researcher also used quotes to indicate that the text had been taken from another paper. Similarly, the researcher assured that honesty was present when working on the manuscript, and no intentional misrepresentation or making up of data or results was included, nor was the researcher purposefully putting forward conclusions that were not accurate.

2.5. Research Participants—Qualitative analyses typically require a smaller sample size than quantitative analyses. Qualitative sample sizes should be large enough to obtain feedback for most perceptions. Obtaining most or all of the perceptions will lead to saturation. Saturation occurs when more participants are added to the study, which does not result in additional perspectives or information. Glaser and Strauss (1967) recommend the concept of saturation for achieving an appropriate sample size in qualitative studies. For phenomenological studies, Creswell (1998) recommends five (5) to 25, and Morse (1994) suggests at least six (6). There are no specific rules when determining an appropriate sample size in qualitative research. Qualitative sample size may best be determined by the time allotted, resources available, and study objectives (Patton, 1990). The participants of this study were Eight (8) teachers from Pantukan South District, Division of de Oro. The participants were chosen based on the following criteria: (1) must be in the service for at least 5 years; (2) elementary school teacher; and (3) experienced in SBM evaluation. The researcher utilized the purposive sampling design since the participants were chosen based on the criteria or purpose of the study (Creswell, 2014). It is also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling. The selection of the participants was purposefully done to ensure that the findings would be authentic (Marshall, 1996).

2.6. Role of the Researcher—The researcher is responsible for uncovering, transferring, and exploiting knowledge to benefit educa-

tional institutions. To do so, the researcher takes up the following roles in the course of the study: Facilitator and Promoter of Unbiased Research. The researcher conducts interviews with the participants and guides them in the process. The researcher interprets ideas and responses based on existing literature and related studies and not on the researcher's knowledge, thoughts, and feelings to avoid the intrusion of bias. Expert in qualitative methods. The researcher implements the qualitative method correctly. To do so, the researcher assesses himself and seeks help from the research adviser and other professionals. These help him demonstrate competence in explaining the study without biasing the participants, conducting interviews according to the design, making appropriate field observations, selecting appropriate artifacts, images, and journal portions, and employing Environmental Triangulation and Thematic Content Analysis precisely. Collector and Keeper of data. The researcher ensures different ways of making a record of what is said and done during the interview and Focus Group Discussion, such as taking handwritten notes or audio and/or video recording. The recordings are transcribed verbatim before data analysis can begin. Records done by the researcher are adequately secured as they contain sensitive information and are relevant to the research. However, the data are being collected, and the researcher's primary responsibility is to safeguard participants and their data. Mechanisms for safeguarding must be clearly articulated to participants and approved by a relevant research ethics review board before the research begins. Analyst of data. The researcher sees the phenomenon or problem from the participants' perspective by interpreting data, transcribing and checking, reading between the lines, coding, and theming. The researcher ensures that the findings are accurate to the participants and that their voices are heard. Organizer and presenter of data. The researcher presents the problem and

the related literature and studies that support it. Findings of the study are presented through research questions – stating the results for each one by using themes to show how the research questions were answered in the study. Moreover, the researcher gives future directions and implications of the study for improving educational policy and practices.

2.7. Data Collection—To ensure safe educational continuity admits the challenge of COVID-19, this study adhered to the Department of Health (DOH) Administrative Order No. 2020-0015 or the Guidelines on the Risk-Based Public Health Standards for COVID-19 Mitigation, cited by the IATF to aid all sectors in all settings to implement non-pharmaceutical interventions. The following is the step-by-step process of gathering the data needed. Securing endorsement from the Dean of Graduate School. The researcher asked for an endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School of Rizal Memorial Colleges as one of the documents needed for submission to the office of the Schools Division Superintendent in asking permission to conduct the study. Asking permission from the Schools Division Superintendent. The researcher asked permission from the Schools Division Superintendent to conduct the study in the identified school. The researcher would send a letter addressed to the Schools Division Superintendent with the attached Chapters 1 and 2 together with the research instrument, which explains the study's objectives and the participants' identification. The researcher would wait for the SDS's response before conducting the study. Asking permission from the school heads. After securing the approval of the SDS, the researcher sent letters to the principals of the schools explaining the study to be conducted in their schools. Obtaining consent from the participants. The researcher asked permission from the participants and to their parents/guardians. They were formally oriented about the study and of the process they shall go through as participants. Con-

ducting the interview. The researcher conducted the in-depth interview using the interview questionnaire. The profile of the participants was taken, notes were jotted down, and conversations were recorded using a sound recorder for ease of transcription. The researcher carefully listened and responded actively during the interviews. The researcher transcribed the interviewees' responses precisely by recalling their answers from the sound recorder. Since the participants used their vernacular language, the researcher translated it into English. Data Coding and Thematic Content Analysis. After the transcription, the data will then be categorized and coded. Then, themes were extracted, and individual participant data was compared and contrasted. The researcher then conducted a second round of interviews (FGD) to corroborate any data that needed further explanation and input from the participants; additional information gathered was examined thoroughly and integrated into the existing body of data. After this, data were compared and contrasted between the participants in order to come up with patterns and trends.

2.8. Data Analysis—In this study, thematic analysis was utilized to analyze the gathered data. The researcher analyzed the answers of the participants from the conducted interviews using Creswell's Model, specifically the identifying of themes approach. According to Creswell (2012), themes in qualitative research are similar codes aggregated together to form a major idea in the database. Familiarization with the data was common to all forms of qualitative analysis, the researcher immersed herself in, and became intimately familiar with, their data; reading and re-reading the data and noting any initial analytic observations. Coding was also a common element of many approaches to qualitative analysis, involving generating pithy labels for important features of the data of relevance to the (broad) research question guiding the analysis. Coding was not simply a data re-

duction method; it was also an analytic process, so codes capture both a semantic and conceptual reading of the data. The researcher coded every data item and ended this phase by collating all their codes and relevant data extracts. Searching for themes was a coherent and meaningful pattern in the data relevant to the research question. The researcher ended this phase by collating all the coded data relevant to each theme. Reviewing themes. The researcher reflected on whether the themes tell a convincing and compelling story about the data and began to define the nature of each individual theme and the relationship between the themes. For these, Thematic Content Analysis was employed by the researcher. Thematic Content Analysis was a descriptive presentation of qualitative data in which a detailed analysis of each theme was made by identifying the 'essence' of each theme and constructing a concise, punchy and informative name for each theme (Andersen, 2013). In addition, to enhance validity and to create a more in-depth picture of the phenomenon, Environmental Triangulation was also employed by the researcher. It was a technique to analyze the same study's results using different data collection methods. The key was identifying which environmental factors might influence the information received during the study. These environmental factors are changed to see if the findings are the same across the settings (David, 2015). This type of triangulation uses different settings, locations, and other factors such as time, day, and season in which the study occurred. The idea was to determine which factors influence the information received; these factors are then changed to see if the findings are the same. Validity can be established if the findings remain unaltered under varying environmental factors (Naeem, Saira, 2019). In this study, such triangulation was used considering that the requirement, as mentioned, was the use of environmental triangulation best suited to the environment of the research being conducted.

Writing up involves weaving together the analytic narrative and data extracts to tell the reader a coherent and persuasive story about the data and contextualizing it about existing literature.

2.9. Analytical Framework—The framework analysis of this research was flexible to allow the researcher to either collect all the data and then analyze it or do data analysis during the collection process. The gathered data was sifted, charted, and sorted by key issues and themes in the analysis stage. This involves a five-step process: (1) familiarization, (2) identifying a thematic framework, (3) indexing, (4) charting, and (5) mapping and interpretation (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). Familiarization refers to the process during which the researcher becomes familiarized with the transcripts of the data collected that was interview or focus group transcripts, observation, or field notes and gains an overview of the collected data (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). In other words, the researcher becomes immersed in the data by listening to audiotapes, studying the field, or reading the transcripts. Throughout this process, the researcher would become aware of key ideas and recurrent themes and make a note of them. Due to the sheer volume of data that can be collected in qualitative research, the researcher may be unable to review all the material. Thus, a selection of the data set would be utilized. The selection would depend on several aspects of the data collection process. For example, the mix of methods used (e.g., interviews, documents, observations), The second stage of identifying a thematic framework occurs after familiarization when the researcher recognizes emerging themes or issues in the data set. These emerging themes or issues may have arisen from a priori themes; however, the researcher must allow the data to dictate the themes and issues at this stage. The researcher uses the notes taken during the familiarization stage to achieve this. The key issues, concepts, and themes expressed by the participants now form the basis of a thematic framework that can

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study filter and classify the data (Ritchie Spencer, 1994).

Figure 2 shows the steps in the study’s analytical framework, which involves familiarization, coding, developing a thematic framework, indexing, charting, mapping, and interpretation. Indexing means identifying data portions or sections corresponding to a particular theme. This process is applied to all the textual data that has been gathered (e.g., transcripts of interviews). For convenience, Ritchie and Spencer recommend that a numerical system be used to index references and annotated in the margin beside the text (1994). Qualitative data analysis tools are ideal for such a task. The final stage, mapping, and interpretation, involves the analysis of the key characteristics as laid out in the charts. This analysis should be able to provide a schematic diagram of the event/phenomenon, thus guiding the researcher in their interpretation of the data set. At this point, the researcher was cognizant of the objectives of qualitative analysis: “defining concepts, map-

ping range and nature of phenomena, creating typologies, finding associations, providing explanations, and developing strategies” (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). Once again, these concepts, technologies, and associations reflect the participant. Therefore, any strategy or recommendations made by the researcher echo the participants’ attitudes, beliefs, and values.

2.10. *Trustworthiness of the Study*—Trustworthiness was all about establishing credibility, transferability, confirmability, and dependability. In qualitative study, trustworthiness was significant because the research study’s result and finding would depend on how the researcher was conducting it. The trustworthiness of a research study is important to evaluate its worth. Due to the nature of the qualitative study, honesty in all the data and details is required. Trustworthiness makes the researcher’s study worthy to read, share, and be proud of. Credibility was how confident the qualitative researcher

was in the truth of the research study's findings. The researcher in this study believed that honesty in everything you do was essential to attain worthwhile success. The researcher has no derogatory records or administrative issues that ruin her integrity. Lincoln and Guba (2000) state that credibility refers to the idea of internal consistency, where the main issue is "how we ensure rigor in the research process and how we communicate to others that we have done so." Transferability is how the qualitative researcher demonstrates that the research study's findings apply to other contexts. In this case, "other contexts" can mean similar situations, similar populations, and similar phenomena. The researcher has already studied the effects of using a graphic organizer as a strategy for teaching reading comprehension. Using graphic organizers as a strategy in teaching reading comprehension is effective in the domains of analysis and creation. With this, the researcher is interested in the students' perspective on using this strategy. Gasson (2004) emphasizes transferability as the extent to which the reader is able to provide a generalization of the study based on his own context and can able to address the core issue of "how far a researcher may make claims for a general application of the theory." Confirmability was the degree of neutrality in the research study's findings. In other words, this means that the findings are based on participants' responses and not any potential bias

or personal motivations of the researcher. This involves ensuring that researcher bias does not skew the interpretation of what the research participants said to fit a particular narrative. The information using the audit trail in this situation is thoughtfully recorded by the researcher, which highlights every step of data analysis that was made in order to provide a rationale for the decisions made. This helps establish that the research study's findings accurately portray participants' responses. Gasson (2004) states that confirmability was based on acknowledging that research is never objective. Dependability was the extent that other researchers could repeat the study and that the findings would be consistent. In other words, if a person wanted to replicate your study, they should have enough information from your research report to do so and obtain similar findings as your study did. A qualitative researcher uses an inquiry audit in order to establish dependability, which requires an outside person to review and examine the research process and the data analysis in order to ensure that the findings are consistent and can be repeated. In this component, the use of a database was essential in backing up information collected and noting changes for all types of research studies. All the data collected was kept correctly for future use as references. Gasson (2004) stated that dependability deals with the core issue of "the way in which a study is conducted.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter discusses the presentation of results, the analysis, and the interpretation of data gathered. This is done through a thematic approach where the exposition of transcripts as responses of the participants using pseudonyms to hide the profile in verbatim forms and figures are produced. Words of opinions from the authors in a related study and literature are also given importance to back up claims and make sound discussions. Thus, the following responses are grouped based on the problem statement.

3.1. Lived Experiences of School-based Management Evaluators during Post-pandemic —School-based management (SBM) is a system of school governance that empowers educators,

parents, and community members to take an active role in a school's decision-making process. It is a decentralized approach to school management that aims to improve student learning outcomes by giving stakeholders more control over how resources are allocated, teaching and learning are carried out, and how schools are evaluated. As an SBM evaluator member, I must have a deep understanding of the principles that underlie this approach to school governance. Currently, lived experience involvement in evaluation is generally focused on data collection. People with lived experience are data points. They provide their information to evaluations through the sharing of their stories, personal data, and experiences. Not always, but often, this runs the risk that evaluations are extractive. They draw on our experiences without facilitating our input into the other fundamental processes of conducting an evaluation. One understanding of evaluation is that it is about understanding whether an intervention has been implemented to anticipated standards or delivered expected outcomes. If evaluators limit lived experience engagement to data collection, people with lived experience are always dancing on a stage built by someone else. An SBM evaluator member requires a deep understanding of the principles that underlie this approach to school governance. These principles include a commitment to SBM's goals and objectives, a deep understanding of the school community's needs and priorities, a comprehensive understanding of the school's internal and external environment, and a strong commitment to continuous improvement. By embodying these principles, SBM evaluator members can help improve student learning outcomes and create a more effective and efficient school system.

3.1.1. Challenged Perspectives—Challenged perspectives in the context of SBM evaluation refer to stakeholders' differing expectations, beliefs, and priorities regarding what constitutes good school performance and im-

provement. These differing perspectives can make it challenging for SBM evaluators to interpret and communicate the evaluation results effectively to stakeholders. As an SBM evaluator, it is essential to have an open mind and to be willing to engage with different perspectives to ensure that SBM strategies are effective and inclusive. However, encountering challenges with different perspectives can be a difficult and even uncomfortable experience. While these studies are accurate, the SBM members of evaluation team have shared their experiences during their conduct of evaluation amongst school in the post pandemic. Given that we have a hard lockdown, the schools have their own initiatives to facilitate the SBM evaluation process. In the Philippine setting, evaluators encounter different perspectives from various stakeholders, including school administrators, teachers, students, and parents. According to Esquivel (2018), the Philippine educational system is undergoing significant changes, which may result in different stakeholder perspectives. These changes include implementing the K-12 program, the shift to outcome-based education, and the increasing use of technology in teaching and learning. These changes may challenge traditional beliefs and practices, leading to diverse perspectives and potential stakeholder conflicts. According to De Jesus (2015), cultural and linguistic diversity can be challenging for the Philippine educational system, as it may result in different perspectives on teaching and learning. Additionally, using different languages in education can lead to communication barriers, making it difficult to understand and respect different perspectives. Finally, SBM evaluators in the Philippine setting can adopt a reflective and open-minded approach to dealing with different perspectives. According to Meris (2016), reflective practice involves critically examining one's own assumptions and beliefs and being open to new ideas and perspectives. By adopting this approach, SBM evaluators can promote

continuous learning and growth and improve the effectiveness of SBM strategies. In conclusion, being challenged with perspectives is one of the lived experiences of an SBM evaluator in the Philippine setting. SBM evaluators can manage this challenge by developing cultural competence, adopting a participatory and inclusive approach, and adopting a reflective and open-minded approach. By embracing different perspectives and promoting inclusivity, SBM evaluators can contribute to developing a more effective and inclusive Philippine educational system.

3.1.2. Threatened Validity and Reliability—Threatened validity and reliability in the context of SBM (School-Based Management) evaluation refer to the risks of inaccuracies and inconsistencies in the evaluation results that can compromise their usefulness and credibility. Validity refers to the extent to which the evaluation measures what it is supposed to measure, while reliability refers to the consistency and stability of the evaluation results over time and across different evaluators. If the validity and reliability of the SBM evaluation results are threatened, the interpretation and use of these results may be affected. For example, if the evaluation criteria are not clearly defined, or if the evaluation process is not rigorous or standardized, the evaluation results may not accurately reflect the school's performance. In such cases, the validity of the evaluation results is threatened. Similarly, if the evaluation process is inconsistent or prone to bias, the reliability of the evaluation results is threatened. One of the main concerns of SBM evaluators is ensuring the validity and reliability of the evaluation results. According to Singh and Garg (2018), validity refers to the accuracy and meaningfulness of the evaluation results, while reliability refers to the consistency and stability of the evaluation results over time. Ensuring the validity and reliability of the evaluation results is crucial to establish the credibility and usefulness of the evaluation. However, the

validity and reliability of the evaluation results can be threatened by various factors. For instance, according to Petrarca, Lopes, and Esteban (2016), the lack of clarity and agreement on the objectives and standards of the evaluation can lead to inconsistencies and subjectivity in the evaluation results. Additionally, the lack of resources and support for the evaluation process can compromise the validity and reliability of the evaluation results. According to Dika and Rachmawati (2017), stakeholders may resist the evaluation process if they perceive it as a threat to their interests or a challenge to their authority. This resistance can lead to biased or incomplete information, compromising the validity and reliability of the evaluation results. To address the challenge of threatened validity and reliability, SBM evaluators can adopt various strategies. One strategy is to establish clear and objective evaluation criteria and standards, as well as clear communication with stakeholders regarding the purpose and process of the evaluation. This can promote transparency and reduce the potential for biases and subjectivity. Therefore, it is important for SBM evaluators to ensure that the evaluation process is valid and reliable by using clear and well-defined evaluation criteria, conducting rigorous and standardized evaluations, and implementing appropriate quality control measures. This helps to ensure that the evaluation results are accurate, reliable, and useful for improving school performance. The participants have shared their responses given their experiences during the conduct of the SBM evaluation during post pandemic school year. Validity and reliability on the process are importance factors to consider the success of the evaluation. School-Based Management (SBM) in the Philippines has been implemented for over two decades now, and it has faced challenges in terms of ensuring the validity and reliability of the evaluation results. SBM evaluators, who are typically school principals or administrators, have experienced threats to the validity and re-

liability of the evaluation process and results. One of the challenges faced by SBM evaluators is the lack of knowledge and skills in conducting valid and reliable evaluations. As noted by Tuy (2015), SBM evaluators may not have sufficient training or experience in conducting evaluations, which can lead to inaccurate or inconsistent evaluation results. This lack of expertise can also result in a lack of trust from stakeholders in the evaluation process and the validity and reliability of the results. In the Philippines, schools with high evaluation ratings are often given more resources and funding, while those with low ratings may face consequences such as reduced funding or staff reassignments. This pressure to produce positive results can lead to evaluators manipulating data or altering evaluation criteria to ensure positive outcomes (Cahapay, 2017). Additionally, SBM evaluators may face challenges in ensuring the participation and engagement of stakeholders, such as parents, teachers, and students, in the evaluation process. The participation of stakeholders is crucial in ensuring the validity and reliability of the evaluation results, but it can be challenging to engage them and ensure their participation (Aguja, 2019). In conclusion, the lived experience of SBM evaluators in the Philippines includes challenges in ensuring the validity and reliability of the evaluation process and results. These challenges include a lack of knowledge and skills, pressure to produce positive results, and difficulties engaging stakeholders. To address these challenges, SBM evaluators need sufficient training and support, accountability, and stakeholder engagement to ensure the validity and reliability of the evaluation process and results.

3.1.3. Differed Interpretation—Differed interpretation in the context of SBM (School-Based Management) evaluation refers to the varying perspectives and understandings among stakeholders regarding the meaning and implications of the evaluation results. Different stake-

holders, such as school administrators, teachers, students, parents, and community members, may have differing expectations, beliefs, and priorities regarding what constitutes good school performance and improvement. These differing perspectives can result in differences in interpreting the evaluation results. For example, some stakeholders may view high test scores as the primary indicator of a successful school, while others may prioritize a supportive school culture and positive student outcomes. This can lead to conflicting interpretations of the evaluation results and make it difficult for SBM evaluators to develop strategies for improvement that are acceptable to all stakeholders. To address these challenges, SBM evaluators must communicate effectively with stakeholders to clarify the evaluation criteria and objectives, explain the meaning and implications of the evaluation results, and work to reconcile differing perspectives and priorities. By doing so, they can ensure that the evaluation results are correctly understood and used to inform improvement efforts in a way that meets the needs and expectations of all stakeholders. School-Based Management (SBM) is an approach to educational management that involves the participation of stakeholders, including school administrators, teachers, parents, and students. SBM evaluation is an essential component of this approach, which aims to improve the quality of education by evaluating school performance and identifying areas for improvement. However, the interpretation of the SBM evaluation results can differ among stakeholders, leading to conflicts and challenges for SBM evaluators. One of the challenges faced by SBM evaluators is the differing interpretation of the evaluation results among stakeholders. This can occur when stakeholders have different expectations or perspectives on what constitutes good performance or improvement. For example, parents may prioritize the academic performance of their children, while teachers may focus on the development of criti-

Fig. 3. Emerging Themes on the Lived Experiences of School-based Management Evaluators

cal thinking skills. These differing perspectives can make it challenging for SBM evaluators to interpret the evaluation results and communicate them effectively to stakeholders (Wei Li, 2019). Another challenge is the conflicting interests and priorities of stakeholders. In some cases, stakeholders may have conflicting interests and priorities that can impact their interpretation of the evaluation results. For example, school administrators may be more concerned with maintaining the school’s reputation or securing funding, while teachers may prioritize the needs of their students. These conflicting interests can make it challenging for SBM evaluators to interpret the evaluation results and develop strategies for improvement that are acceptable to all stakeholders (Cheng, 2015). According to the participants, differed interpretation can create small conflicts and the challenge is how to mitigate them. For example school administrators may be more concerned with maintaining the school’s reputation or securing funding, while teachers may prioritize the needs of their students. These conflicting interests can make it challenging for SBM evaluators to interpret the evaluation results and develop strategies for improvement that are acceptable to all stakeholders. What the SBM evaluators in the

Philippines face is the differing interpretation of evaluation results among stakeholders. For instance, parents may prioritize the academic performance of their children, while teachers may focus on developing critical thinking skills. These different perspectives can make it challenging for SBM evaluators to interpret the evaluation results and communicate them effectively to stakeholders (Abraham, 2017). Another challenge is the lack of understanding of the evaluation process and criteria among stakeholders. Some stakeholders may not fully understand the criteria used in the evaluation, which can lead to misinterpretation of the results. This can cause confusion and dissatisfaction among stakeholders and can be challenging for SBM evaluators to manage (Bautista Bautista, 2018). SBM evaluators in the Philippines need to engage in effective communication with stakeholders and promote stakeholder participation in the evaluation process. This can help to ensure that all stakeholders have a clear understanding of the evaluation results and the strategies for improvement. SBM evaluators can also provide training to stakeholders on the evaluation process and criteria, which can improve their understanding and interpretation of the evaluation results (Fernandez, 2020).

In conclusion, the lived experience of SBM evaluators in the Philippine setting includes challenges in interpreting SBM evaluation results due to differing perspectives, conflicting interests and priorities, and lack of understanding of the evaluation process and criteria among stakeholders. Effective communication and stakeholder participation are essential in addressing these challenges and ensuring that the evaluation results are interpreted and communicated effectively to all stakeholders.

3.2. Coping with Challenges to Overcome in School-based Management Evaluation during post pandemic—As schools transitioned to remote and hybrid learning models, SBM evaluators were required to adapt their evaluation methods and tools to assess the effectiveness of these new modes of instruction. In addition to these technical challenges, SBM evaluators also faced a range of social and emotional challenges, including increased stress and anxiety among students, teachers, and administrators. To cope with these challenges, SBM evaluators have had to be creative and flexible in their approach to evaluation. Some of the strategies that SBM evaluators have used during the post-pandemic period include: Adopting new evaluation methods: SBM evaluators have had to adapt their evaluation methods to assess the effectiveness of remote and hybrid learning models. This has included using online surveys, video conferences, and virtual classroom observations to gather data on student performance and teacher practices. SBM evaluators have recognized the importance of engaging stakeholders, including teachers, students, parents, and community members, in the evaluation process. By doing so, they can ensure that the evaluation results are relevant and actionable. SBM evaluators have recognized that the pandemic has been a stressful and challenging time for many stakeholders. They have therefore made an effort to be empathetic and understanding in their interactions with stakeholders. SBM

evaluators have emphasized the importance of using data to inform decision-making. By analyzing the evaluation results, they can identify areas of strength and weakness in school performance and develop strategies for improvement. SBM evaluators have recognized that effective evaluation requires collaboration and teamwork among stakeholders. They have therefore encouraged stakeholders to work together to identify areas for improvement and develop strategies to address them. In conclusion, SBM evaluators have faced significant challenges during the post-pandemic period. However, by adopting new evaluation methods, prioritizing stakeholder engagement, being sensitive to the emotional needs of stakeholders, using data to inform decision-making, and encouraging collaboration and teamwork, they have been able to cope with these challenges and continue to improve school performance.

3.2.1. Build Harmonious Working Relationship—Building a harmonious working relationship among SBM evaluators is essential in ensuring the success of school-based management evaluations. A harmonious working relationship fosters open communication, trust, and mutual respect, which are necessary for effective collaboration and teamwork. In an international setting, where cultural differences and language barriers may exist, building a harmonious working relationship can be particularly challenging. Several authors have emphasized the importance of building a harmonious working relationship among SBM evaluators. For instance, in their 2019 study, Zheng and colleagues explored the factors that contribute to successful SBM evaluations in China. They found that building a collaborative relationship among stakeholders was critical in ensuring the success of the evaluation. The authors highlighted the importance of establishing a shared vision and goals, developing trust among stakeholders, and creating a supportive and respectful working environment. Similarly, in a 2020

study on SBM evaluation in Malaysia, Hooi and colleagues identified communication and collaboration as key factors in achieving successful evaluations. The authors emphasized the importance of building relationships based on mutual trust and respect, establishing clear lines of communication, and promoting open and honest dialogue among stakeholders. Odeleye and Oladele (2021) emphasized the importance of cultural sensitivity and understanding. They highlighted the need for SBM evaluators to be aware of cultural differences and to take steps to accommodate these differences in their evaluation processes. The authors suggested that SBM evaluators should make an effort to learn about local customs and traditions, communicate clearly and respectfully, and be open to feedback and criticism. In the Philippine setting, building a harmonious working relationship is one of the coping mechanisms among SBM evaluators when faced with challenges in school-based management evaluation. This involves the establishment of positive and respectful communication, collaboration, and trust among stakeholders in the evaluation process. Through this approach, SBM evaluators can enhance their ability to navigate complex situations and ultimately improve the effectiveness of the evaluation process. A study conducted by Fajardo, et al. (2019) explored the factors that contribute to the success of school-based management evaluation in the Philippines. One of the key findings was that the development of strong relationships between the evaluators and the school personnel is crucial to ensuring that the evaluation is conducted effectively. The study recommended the use of participatory approaches to evaluation, which can foster collaboration and trust among stakeholders. Similarly, a study by Canencia and Cantoria (2020) highlighted the importance of building a positive and respectful working relationship among SBM evaluators, teachers, and other school personnel. The authors emphasized the need for evalua-

tors to establish open communication channels with school personnel, to actively listen to their concerns, and to be responsive to their needs. Through this approach, evaluators can build trust and rapport with school personnel, which can help to address challenges in the evaluation process. Another study by Gonzales (2022) emphasized the importance of promoting a culture of collaboration among SBM evaluators and school personnel. The author recommended the use of a co-evaluation approach, which involves the active participation of school personnel in the evaluation process. In conclusion, building a harmonious working relationship is a vital coping mechanism for SBM evaluators when faced with challenges in the school-based management evaluation process. The establishment of positive and respectful communication, collaboration, and trust among stakeholders can enhance the effectiveness of the evaluation process. Participatory approaches to evaluation, open communication channels, and the use of a co-evaluation approach are among the strategies that SBM evaluators can use to build strong relationships with school personnel and navigate complex situations.

3.2.2. *Do Tasks as Fun for Newer Learning*—Doing tasks as fun for new learning in the context of coping mechanism is an approach that focuses on incorporating enjoyable and engaging activities to facilitate learning and reduce stress among SBM evaluators. It is the act of promoting a positive attitude towards work by creating a fun and interactive environment where evaluators can enjoy the process of learning and growing in their roles. This approach involves designing activities that are challenging and exciting, encouraging collaboration and teamwork, and providing opportunities for continuous learning and improvement. Doing tasks as fun for new learning involves a mindset that views challenges and setbacks as opportunities for growth and development rather than sources of stress and frustration. It is an

effective strategy to boost morale, increase motivation, and promote a sense of accomplishment among SBM evaluators. As a result, SBM evaluators face various challenges that can affect their productivity and well-being. To address these challenges, SBM evaluators must adopt effective coping mechanisms to overcome stress and adapt to the new normal. One such coping mechanism is doing tasks with fun for new learning, which emphasizes the incorporation of enjoyable and engaging activities to facilitate learning and reduce stress among SBM evaluators. According to Nastiti and Ulfah (2021), doing tasks with fun can be an effective way to boost morale and motivation among evaluators. They noted that incorporating enjoyable and challenging tasks, such as quizzes and games, can create a more engaging and dynamic learning environment. Similarly, Smeets and Bus (2019) argued that fun and games can be used as effective tools to promote active learning, encourage collaboration and teamwork, and increase motivation among learners. Ayas et al. (2019) highlighted the importance of incorporating humor and positive emotions in learning. They argued that humor can effectively reduce stress and promote a positive attitude toward work. SBM evaluators can adopt this approach by incorporating humorous anecdotes and jokes to create a lighter and more enjoyable work environment. Doing tasks with fun for new learning can be an effective coping mechanism among SBM evaluators in the international setting. It can promote a positive attitude towards work, increase motivation, and reduce stress. Incorporating enjoyable and challenging tasks, using technology, and integrating humor and positive emotions can create a more engaging and dynamic learning environment. SBM evaluators must adopt this approach to overcome the challenges posed by the pandemic and the new normal in education. Coping mechanisms are essential in ensuring the success of any organization, and SBM evaluators are not exempted

from experiencing challenges that need coping mechanisms. In the Philippine setting, SBM evaluators face various challenges in their work, such as workload, resource constraints, and limited time, which can affect their performance and well-being. One coping mechanism that can help SBM evaluators overcome these challenges is doing tasks with fun for new learning. Doing tasks with fun for new learning is a coping mechanism that aims to provide a positive and enjoyable work experience while promoting continuous learning and growth. SBM evaluators who practice this mechanism view their tasks as opportunities to learn and explore new ideas rather than just routine tasks that must be completed. By doing tasks with a positive mindset, SBM evaluators can increase their motivation and engagement in their work, resulting in better performance and well-being. In conclusion, doing tasks with fun for new learning is a coping mechanism that can help SBM evaluators overcome the challenges they face in their work. Studies in international and Philippine settings have shown the importance of creating a positive and enjoyable work environment, providing training and development opportunities, and promoting collaboration and cooperation among SBM evaluators. By practicing this coping mechanism, SBM evaluators can improve their performance, well-being, and overall job satisfaction.

3.2.3. Collaborate and Cooperate—Collaboration and cooperation in the context of coping mechanisms involve working together as a team to achieve a common goal or objective. It combines individual strengths, skills, and knowledge to create a unified effort towards a shared outcome. Collaboration and cooperation entail open communication, active listening, and a willingness to compromise and work towards a shared objective. It involves recognizing and respecting each other's perspectives, contributions, and experiences and using them to create a more comprehensive and effective

Fig. 4. Emerging Themes in Coping Challenges among SBM Evaluators

outcome. In coping mechanisms, collaboration and cooperation can effectively manage challenges and stress by promoting a supportive and inclusive work culture, fostering a sense of belonging, and reducing the workload and stress associated with individual efforts. Collaboration and cooperation have been identified as important coping mechanisms among School-Based Management (SBM) evaluators in dealing with the challenges brought about by the pandemic. According to Saleem, Sabiha, and Abideen (2019), collaboration involves working toward a common goal, while cooperation refers to working together to achieve a specific task or project. These concepts are important in the context of SBM evaluation because the process involves the participation of multiple stakeholders, including school administrators, teachers, parents, and students. In the international setting, SBM evaluators collaborate and cooperate through various means, including virtual meetings and online platforms. For instance, in a study by Ali and Waseem (2021), SBM evaluators in Pakistan reported using online platforms such as Zoom and Google Meet

to communicate and collaborate with their team members. The authors noted that this approach allowed the evaluators to stay connected and share their experiences and strategies for coping with the challenges brought about by the pandemic. Similarly, in a study by Bhattacharya et al. (2021) in India, SBM evaluators were found to be collaborating with teachers and school administrators to develop innovative solutions for delivering education during the pandemic. The authors noted that this approach helped to build trust and fostered a sense of community among the stakeholders involved in the evaluation process. Ablaza and Saludes (2021) emphasized the importance of collaboration and cooperation among SBM evaluators in the Philippines, particularly during the pandemic. The study found that the pandemic brought about significant changes in the evaluation process, and SBM evaluators had to work together to adapt to these changes. The study highlighted that cooperation and collaboration were essential in ensuring that the evaluation process continued despite the challenges brought about by the pandemic.

In conclusion, collaboration and cooperation are crucial coping mechanisms among SBM evaluators in the Philippines. These mechanisms enable SBM evaluators to effectively and efficiently evaluate the effectiveness of

the country's school-based management system. Through collaboration and cooperation, SBM evaluators can ensure that the evaluation process is accurate, reliable, and relevant.

3.3. *Educational management insights can be drawn from the school-based management evaluation*—School-based Management (SBM) Evaluation is a comprehensive process that evaluates the effectiveness of school management practices, including leadership, decision-making, resource management, and community engagement. SBM evaluation provides important insights into the current state of the school’s management and identifies areas for improvement. In turn, SBM evaluation can provide valuable educational management insights for SBM evaluators, helping them improve their understanding of school management practices and informing their future work. One key educational management insight that can be drawn from SBM evaluation is the importance of effective leadership. SBM evaluation can identify whether a school has a strong and effective leader who can lead it toward its goals, create a positive school culture, and make effective decisions. Another educational management insight that can be gained from SBM evaluation is the importance of community engagement. SBM evaluation can identify whether a school engages effectively with its community, including parents, local organizations, and businesses. Effective community engagement is critical for improving student outcomes and ensuring the school meets its community’s needs. SBM evaluation can also provide insights into resource management. Evaluators can learn how a school manages its resources, including its budget, facilities, and staff. They can gain insights into effective resource management strategies, such as using data to inform resource allocation and strategically invest in staff development. These insights can inform future resource management practices in other schools.

3.3.1. *Review Policy Framework*—In educational learning insight, a review policy framework refers to a structured process of evaluating and analyzing existing policies and practices to determine their effectiveness in achieving

desired educational outcomes. This process involves gathering data and feedback from various stakeholders, such as students, teachers, parents, and community members, and using this information to identify areas for improvement and make evidence-based decisions on policy changes. The review policy framework allows educational institutions to ensure that their policies and practices align with their goals and objectives and meet the needs of their stakeholders. It also provides an opportunity to continuously monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of policies and practices to make informed decisions for future improvements. School-based management (SBM) has been implemented in many countries to improve the quality of education by empowering school communities to be more involved in decision-making processes. As a result, SBM evaluators are responsible for assessing the effectiveness of SBM practices in schools. However, SBM evaluation is not only about assessing schools’ performance but also provides a platform to identify areas for improvement and review the SBM policy framework. According to Kauppi et al. (2021), SBM evaluators should provide feedback to policymakers regarding the strengths and weaknesses of the SBM policy framework. This feedback can assist policymakers in understanding the challenges and opportunities of implementing SBM in schools. Shah et al. (2019) state that SBM evaluators should analyze the policy framework to identify SBM’s objectives, principles, and standards. This can help evaluators to develop a clear understanding of the SBM goals and how they can be achieved. In addition, SBM evaluators can also assess the alignment of the SBM policy framework with national education policies and goals. Furthermore, reviewing the policy framework of SBM can provide insights into the factors that influence the success or failure of SBM practices. According to Ahmed and Mushtaq (2019), SBM evaluators should analyze the policy framework to identify the factors

that support or hinder the implementation of SBM in schools. This can help evaluators better understand schools' challenges in implementing SBM practices. Moreover, this can help evaluators identify the best practices and strategies that can support the implementation of SBM in schools. One educational management insight that can be drawn from reviewing policy frameworks is the need for clear and specific guidelines. According to a study by Tariman et al. (2021), SBM evaluators in the Philippines noted that the lack of specific guidelines often led to confusion and inconsistent program implementation. The study recommended developing a comprehensive and clear set of guidelines to ensure that SBM is implemented consistently and effectively. A study by Ogena and Quina (2021) highlighted the need for active participation and engagement of stakeholders, particularly teachers and school administrators, in developing and implementing SBM policies. The study emphasized that involving stakeholders in the process would enhance the quality of SBM implementation and promote ownership and sustainability of the program. Furthermore, reviewing policy frameworks can provide insights into the need for flexibility and adaptability in SBM implementation. According to a study by Cabigao et al. (2019), SBM evaluators in the Philippines noted that the rigid implementation of policies and guidelines often hindered the effective implementation of the program. The study recommended that SBM policies be flexible enough to allow schools to adapt and respond to their student's and communities' unique needs and circumstances. In conclusion, reviewing policy frameworks is an important aspect of SBM evaluation that can provide educational management insights to evaluators. The need for clear and specific guidelines, stakeholder engagement, and flexibility in implementation are just some of the insights that can be drawn from the review process. SBM evaluators can use these insights to develop and implement poli-

cies to enhance the program's effectiveness and sustainability.

3.3.2. Advocate Continuous Improvement Mechanism—In the context of SBM evaluators' learning insights, a continuous improvement mechanism refers to the ongoing and systematic evaluation and improvement of SBM practices in schools. It involves identifying areas for improvement, setting goals, implementing changes, monitoring progress, and adjusting strategies as needed. Continuous improvement mechanisms also involve creating a culture of learning and innovation in schools where teachers, administrators, and stakeholders work collaboratively to improve student learning outcomes. This mechanism allows SBM evaluators to reflect on their evaluation practices, identify areas for improvement, and implement changes to ensure that schools are continuously evolving and improving. Continuous improvement is a crucial aspect of school-based management (SBM) evaluation. SBM evaluators play a key role in advocating for adopting continuous improvement mechanisms in educational institutions. According to Bassett and Sherry (2021), continuous improvement is an ongoing process that allows schools to adapt to changing circumstances and improve their educational outcomes. SBM evaluators can advocate for continuous improvement by encouraging schools to adopt a continuous learning and improvement culture. This involves setting achievable goals, monitoring progress, and making necessary adjustments to improve educational outcomes. Similarly, Al-Fraihat et al. (2020) emphasized the importance of adopting a continuous improvement approach in educational institutions. They noted that this approach can help schools identify their strengths and weaknesses and develop strategies to address them. SBM evaluators can play a key role in facilitating this process by providing schools with data-driven insights and recommendations for improvement. Moreover, Santos (2021) emphasizes the importance of

fostering a culture of continuous improvement in schools. The author notes that schools should adopt a growth mindset, prioritizing learning, collaboration, and innovation. SBM evaluators should advocate for creating a culture of continuous improvement by encouraging schools to embrace new ideas, share best practices, and learn from their mistakes. In conclusion, continuous improvement mechanisms are essential for ensuring that schools provide quality education to students. SBM evaluators should advocate for the adoption of continuous improvement mechanisms, such as the use of data, the development of school improvement plans, and the creation of a culture of continuous improvement. By doing so, SBM evaluators can help schools evolve and adapt to the changing needs of the education sector, ultimately providing better educational outcomes for students.

3.3.3. Upskill Professional Competencies—Upskilling professional competence refers to improving or acquiring new knowledge, skills, and competencies relevant to one’s job responsibilities and professional growth. In the context of SBM evaluators’ learning insights, upskilling professional competence means enhancing their ability to carry out their tasks effectively and efficiently. This may involve attending training programs, workshops, or seminars, reading relevant literature, and networking and collaborating with other professionals in the field. It also includes using technology and other resources to streamline and optimize their work processes. By continuously upskilling their professional competence, SBM evaluators can improve their performance and contribute to the overall success of the SBM program. SBM evaluators play a crucial role in evaluating and monitoring the effectiveness of SBM implementation in schools. In recent years, the implementation of SBM has become more complex, and therefore, SBM evaluators

must continuously improve their professional competence to ensure that they have the necessary skills to carry out their roles effectively. SBM evaluators need to continually update their knowledge and skills to remain effective in their roles. They must have a deep understanding of educational policies and practices and be able to evaluate the implementation of these policies and practices in schools. They must also be able to use data and evidence to make informed decisions about school improvement strategies. In addition, they must have excellent communication skills to effectively communicate their findings and recommendations to school administrators, teachers, and other stakeholders. Therefore, upskilling professional competence is crucial for SBM evaluators to improve their effectiveness and contribute to the improvement of schools. Continuous professional development programs and learning opportunities can give SBM evaluators the necessary skills and knowledge to conduct effective evaluations. These programs can include workshops, seminars, and training sessions. As Gonzales and Tad-y (2019) suggested, these programs should focus on enhancing the evaluators’ knowledge of SBM policies and guidelines and using appropriate evaluation tools and techniques. Moreover, digital technology can also be utilized to upskill the professional competence of SBM evaluators. A study by Garcia and De Vera (2019) recommends using online resources and e-learning modules to provide SBM evaluators with flexible and accessible learning opportunities. In conclusion, upskilling professional competence is a vital learning insight among SBM evaluators in the Philippine context. Through continuous professional development programs and digital technology, SBM evaluators can enhance their knowledge and skills in conducting effective evaluations, ultimately improving SBM practices in schools.

Fig. 5. Emerging Themes on Educational insights can be drawn from the findings of the study

4. Implications and Future Directions

This chapter presents the study’s implications and directions, given the discussion of the results of the analysis of the data gathered. The following findings and implications were based on an analysis of the themes generated and their future directions.

4.1. Findings—Given the results and discussions presented, the following are findings of the narratives of the phenomenology on SBM evaluation and its cessation to strengthen mechanism. On the lived experiences among SBM evaluators, they have been challenged with perspectives. This challenge can be managed through developing cultural competence, engaging in dialogue and collaboration with stakeholders, and being reflective and open-minded. By embracing different perspectives and promoting inclusivity, SBM evaluators can help to create a more effective and inclusive school system. Secondly, given the experience of being threatened and the validity and reliability of results, SBM evaluators need to receive sufficient training and support in conducting valid and reliable evaluations to overcome these challenges. Thus, transparency and accountability are critical to ensuring the validity and reliability of the evaluation process and results. Lastly, I will discuss the experience of having different in-

terpretations and interpreting SBM evaluation results due to differing perspectives, conflicting interests and priorities, and a lack of understanding of the evaluation process and criteria among stakeholders. Effective communication and stakeholder participation is essential in addressing these challenges and ensuring that the evaluation results are interpreted and communicated effectively to all stakeholders. The coping mechanism among SBM evaluators runs through building harmonious working relationships, doing tasks with fun for newer learning, and collaboration and cooperation between and among stakeholders. SBM evaluators have faced significant challenges during the post-pandemic period. However, by adopting new evaluation methods, prioritizing stakeholder engagement, being sensitive to the emotional needs of stakeholders, using data to inform decision-making, and encouraging collaboration and teamwork, they have been able to cope with these challenges and continue to im-

prove school performance. SBM evaluators must adopt effective coping mechanisms to overcome stress and adapt to the new normal. One coping mechanism is doing tasks with fun for new learning, which emphasizes incorporating enjoyable and engaging activities to facilitate learning and reduce stress among SBM evaluators. Educational learning insights and reviewing policy frameworks have contributed much to the authentic evaluation system; advocacy on continuous improvement mechanisms matters for improving processes, and professional competence upskilling means that everyone must upgrade their skills and knowledge. In coping mechanisms, collaboration and cooperation can effectively manage challenges and stress by promoting a supportive and inclusive work culture, fostering a sense of belonging, and reducing the workload and stress associated with individual efforts.

4.2. *Implications*—School-Based Management (SBM) is widely used to improve educational outcomes. It involves decentralizing decision-making authority from higher levels of administration to schools, empowering them to make decisions on resource allocation, curriculum design, and teacher professional development. The evaluation process of SBM is crucial in assessing its effectiveness in achieving its intended goals. The following are the implications: The challenges given experiences faced by the SBM evaluation on differing perspectives, threatened validity and reliability, and differed interpretations involve a shift in decision-making authority from higher levels of administration to schools, which can result in conflicting views on how to measure its effectiveness. Different stakeholders, such as parents, teachers, administrators, and policymakers, may have varying views on what constitutes effective SBM. This can lead to disagreements on the metrics used to evaluate SBM and the outcomes that should be measured. These differing perspectives can make it challenging to reach

a consensus on the best way to evaluate SBM, potentially leading to a lack of agreement on its effectiveness. Engaging stakeholders in the evaluation process can build trust and collaboration, improving the implementation of SBM. By involving all stakeholders, evaluators can better understand each group's needs and priorities and ensure that the evaluation metrics used align with the goals of SBM. Adopting a mixed-methods approach and using clear evaluation criteria can help to ensure that the metrics used are valid and reliable. This can address the challenge of threatened validity and reliability, ensuring that the evaluation results accurately reflect the effectiveness of SBM. Finally, adopting coping mechanisms can ensure that the evaluation process is continuous and iterative, with opportunities for ongoing improvement. This can help address any challenges during the evaluation process and ensure that the implementation of SBM is continuously improving. By adopting coping mechanisms, SBM evaluators can help implement SBM effectively and improve educational outcomes. As School-Based Management (SBM) evaluators gain insights into what works and what does not in education governance, they can use these insights to make significant improvements in implementing SBM. SBM evaluators can use their insights to review policy frameworks and identify areas where policy changes may be needed. CI mechanisms, such as quality assurance systems or school improvement plans, can help schools identify areas where they need to improve and track progress over time. By advocating for CI mechanisms, evaluators can help ensure that schools continuously improve and provide high-quality education. SBM evaluators can use their insights to identify areas where professional development is needed to improve school leaders' and teachers' skills and knowledge. By advocating for and providing professional development opportunities, evaluators can help to upskill the professional competence of those involved in

SBM implementation.

4.2.1. Future Directions—The future directions for School-Based Management (SBM) evaluation will depend on education governance's evolving needs and priorities. Here are some possible future directions for SBM evaluation: **Integration of technology:** With the increasing use of technology in education, SBM evaluation may need to incorporate technology-based tools and methods. For example, evaluators may use online surveys or data analysis software to collect and analyze data. Integrating technology can help to streamline the evaluation process and make it more efficient. **Emphasis on equity:** As equity in education becomes a growing concern, SBM evaluation may need to focus more on ensuring equitable implementation. Evaluators may need to collect data on how resources are allocated across schools and how SBM is implemented in schools with different demographic characteristics. This can help identify areas where equity needs to be improved. **Focus on student outcomes:** SBM evaluation may need to emphasize student outcomes, such as academic achievement or social-emotional learning. Evaluators may need to collect data on student outcomes and how they are affected by SBM implementation. This can help identify

effective practices and areas for improvement. **Collaboration and knowledge-sharing:** SBM evaluation may need to prioritize collaboration and knowledge-sharing among evaluators, policymakers, and educators. By building a community of practice around SBM evaluation, stakeholders can learn from each other and share best practices. This can help to improve the quality of SBM evaluation and its impact on education governance. **Adaptation to changing needs:** SBM evaluation may need to adapt to changing needs and priorities in education governance. As new challenges arise, such as pandemics or changes in educational policy, SBM evaluation may need to adjust its methods and focus. This can help ensure that SBM evaluation remains relevant and effective in improving education governance. In conclusion, the future directions for SBM evaluation would depend on education governance's evolving needs and priorities. Integration of technology, emphasis on equity, focus on student outcomes, collaboration and knowledge-sharing, and adaptation to changing needs are all possible future directions for SBM evaluation. By incorporating these directions, SBM evaluation can continue to be a valuable tool for improving education governance and promoting high-quality education.

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